

The following artifacts are submitted to support the reproducibility of the study:

- 1) **Lab Study Protocol** – Provides the detailed procedure followed during the study to ensure availability and transparency.
- 2) **SMT Tools Help Documents** – A collection of links and reference materials used by participants to complete tasks with their assigned tools (*Doppler, HCPVault, Infisical*).
- 3) **Python Script** (*SecureSecret.py*) – Contains minimal code used for each study task. Task 1 contains a hard-coded secret (*CompanySecretToken*) for demonstration purposes which is a placeholder and does not represent any real sensitive information.
- 4) **Raw Study Results** - The raw data used to generate Tables 1 and 2, which summarize participant performance and task completion statistics
- 5) **Screening Survey** - Used to recruit participants and screen their eligibility prior to the study.

Note: The artifact was originally cited in the paper using DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17036161>. The concept DOI is <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17018637>, which always resolves to the most recent version.